

A nonlinear couple stress model for periodic sandwich beams

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Abstract

A geometrically nonlinear model for periodic sandwich structures based on the modified couple stress Timoshenko beam theory with *von Kármán* kinematics is proposed. Constitutive relations for the couple stress beam are derived assuming an antiplane core and then extended for a generic periodic cell. A micromechanical approach based on the structural analysis of a unit cell is proposed and utilized to obtain the stiffness properties of selected periodic sandwich beams. Then, a localization scheme to predict the stress distribution over the faces of the selected beams is defined. The present model is shown to be equivalent to the thick-face sandwich theory for a linear elastic antiplane core cell. Numerical studies validate the present model against three-dimensional finite element models and the thick-face sandwich theory, and compare it with the conventional Timoshenko and couple stress Euler-Bernoulli beam theories. The present model is shown to predict deflections, stresses and buckling loads with good accuracy for different periodic cell setups. The model is able to describe elastic size effects in shear-flexible sandwich beams and the core stiffness influence on membrane and bending stress resultants.

Keywords: Couple stress, Sandwich structures, Timoshenko beam, Sandwich theory, Size effect

1. Introduction

Sandwich panels are lightweight structures composed of two faces separated by a low-density core. Over the past decades, these structures have found numerous applications where high stiffness-to-weight/strength ratios are important, such as in vehicle engineering. The two faces are relatively thin and stiff, whereas the core is comparatively thick and soft. The face and core materials as well as the core topology can be tailored based on the desired mechanical properties [1, 2]. In recent years, technological advances such as aluminium brazing, laser-welding and additive manufacturing have allowed the production of sandwich structures with highly optimized periodic cores, see Fig. 1 and Refs. [3–5] for examples. Continuum modelling is an efficient way to predict their response without discretely modelling all structural details involved.

Continuum models for sandwich structures can be broadly divided into single-layer and layer-wise categories according to the dependency of layer-level variables [6]. Oftentimes, refinements of classical theories are referred to as higher-order theories, such as the works in [7, 8]. Low-complexity single-layer models are used in applications where their through-thickness behavior assumptions

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hold approximately. In particular, first-order shear deformation theories have been used extensively to analyze sandwich beams and plates coupled with standard mechanics or homogenization approaches [3, 9]. Conventional first-order theories are, however, inaccurate near discontinuities such as point forces or restrictive boundary conditions. They assume that cell and structure scales are clearly separated and hence that local effects are negligible. Still, periodic sandwich structures can display scale interactions in the presence of relatively large, flexible cells. To include such interactions, enhanced single-layer sandwich theories have been proposed under different assumptions. In particular, the thick-face sandwich theory [10–12] and other enhanced models that include the effect of thick faces [13, 14] have been used to analyze periodic sandwich structures.

In recent years, non-classical continuum theories regained momentum stimulated by size effect observations in micro- and nanoscale devices [15–20]. In particular, couple stress theories [21, 22] and their extension to beams and plates [23–30] received wide acceptance. Numerous finite element models have been also proposed in their context, some of which are given in [25, 31–33]. Couple stress theories include an additional deformation measure in form of rotation gradients when compared to the conventional Cauchy continuum. In modified couple stress-based beam theories, a single scale-dependent stiffness parameter results, which can be determined analytically or through experiments [34]. Overall, non-classical theories have been shown suitable to model periodic sandwich [32, 35–38] and other lattice structures [39–43] involving different levels of complexity and accuracy. The non-classical stiffness can be readily defined as the cells are periodic and have relatively simple geometry. In the past, this has been done, for instance, through unit cell analysis [32, 36, 37], strain energy considerations [43] and analogy with the thick-face sandwich theory [35, 44].

In this work, we develop a model for periodic sandwich beams based on the modified couple stress Timoshenko beam theory [23, 24]. Constitutive relations are derived assuming an antiplane sandwich core and then extended for a generic periodic cell. Then, a micromechanical approach based on the structural analysis of a unit cell is defined and utilized to determine the stiffness properties of selected periodic sandwich beams. A stress analysis scheme is created to recover the discrete stress distribution at the faces of the selected beams. The model is shown to match the thick-face sandwich beam theory [10–12] in the linear case for an antiplane core. A two-node finite element based on [25], which is utilized to solve the equilibrium equations, is then briefly presented. Examples validate the present model against three-dimensional finite element models and compare it with other one-dimensional theories.

Figure 1: Unit cells of periodic sandwich beams with applications in civil, mechanical and vehicle engineering.

2. Couple stress-based sandwich model

2.1. Couple stress Timoshenko beam

Let us consider the modified couple stress Timoshenko beam theory [21, 23, 24] to construct an equivalent sandwich model that includes the local bending effects arising near discontinuities

Figure 2: Couple stress sandwich beam model with conventions indicated.

such as point loads. Figure 2 shows the general conventions of a couple stress beam of length l and height h . The displacement field of the beam can be written as

$$U_x(x, z) = u(x) + z\phi(x), \quad U_z(x, z) = w(x) \quad (1)$$

where u , w and ϕ are the axial and transverse displacements, and the cross-sectional rotation about the y -axis, respectively. The nonzero strains including the *von Kármán* nonlinearity are [23]

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + z \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} = \epsilon_0 + z\kappa_\phi, \\ \gamma_{xz} &= \phi - \theta, \\ \chi_{xy} &= \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) = \frac{1}{4} (\kappa_\phi + \kappa) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\theta = -\frac{\partial w}{\partial x}$, and χ_{xy} is the curvature related to the macrorotation. The beam model at hand can transmit couple stress m_{xy} , as well as the usual normal stress σ_x and the transverse shear stress τ_{xz} . The axial N , global shear Q_0 and two independent bending stress resultants M_0 and M_l are defined (Fig. 2)

$$N = \int_A \sigma_x dA, \quad Q_0 = K_s \int_A \sigma_{xz} dA, \quad M_0 = \int_A \left(\sigma_x z + \frac{1}{2} m_{xy} \right) dA, \quad M_l = \frac{1}{2} \int_A m_{xy} dA \quad (3)$$

Using the conventions here proposed and following the general steps in [23], the equilibrium equations are obtained for the static case in absence of applied body couples

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} + f = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \bar{Q}}{\partial x} + q = 0, \quad Q_0 - \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (4)$$

where f and q are, respectively, distributed axial and transverse loads, and

$$\bar{Q} = Q_0 + Q_l + N \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}, \quad Q_l = \frac{\partial M_l}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

The boundary conditions, defined at $x = 0$ and $x = l$, are

$$N \text{ or } u, \quad \bar{Q} \text{ or } w, \quad M_0 \text{ or } \phi, \quad M_l \text{ or } \theta \quad (6)$$

Figure 3: (a) General arrangement of a sandwich beam unit cell with positive resultants shown at its corners (b) Sandwich beam with antiplane core: membrane and local bending resultants at sandwich faces.

2.2. Sandwich constitutive model

Consider in Fig. 3a a unit-width sandwich cell composed of two continuous faces and arbitrary periodic core. The vertical cell limits are defined at the centerline of the faces, whose distance characterizes the depth d . The unit cell boundaries at $x = 0, s$ are taken as void except at its four corners, see examples in Fig. 1. The couple stress beam resultants translate into equivalent forces and moments at the corner nodes **1** to **4**. A constitutive model is defined with coupling between normal stress and local curvature, and couple stress and axial strain

$$\sigma_x = Q_{11}\epsilon_x + Q_{13}\chi_{xy}, \quad \sigma_{xz} = Q_{22}\gamma_{xz}, \quad 2m_{xy} = Q_{31}\epsilon_x + Q_{33}\chi_{xy} \quad (7)$$

where $Q_{13} = Q_{31}$ results from coordinate system invariance of the constitutive equations and symmetry of the stress tensor.

2.2.1. Antiplane core

Consider the simplifying assumption that the core stiffness contribution to normal and couple stresses is negligible, $\sigma_c \approx 0$. The faces are then modelled as uncoupled conventional beams subjected to membrane forces and bending moments that induce axial and bending face stresses (Fig. 3b)

$$\sigma_i^{(0)} = E_i\epsilon_0 + E_i(z - z_i(z))\kappa_\phi, \quad \sigma_i^{(1)} = E_i z_i(z)\kappa, \quad i = t, b \quad (8)$$

where $z_i = z - z_i^0$ is the vertical coordinate of the local coordinate system of each face with origin at z_i^0

$$z_t^0 = \frac{h}{2} - \frac{t_t}{2}, \quad z_b^0 = -\frac{h}{2} + \frac{t_b}{2} \quad (9)$$

The stress components of the couple stress beam are defined

$$\sigma_i^{(0)} \equiv \sigma_x, \quad \sigma_i^{(0)} z \equiv \sigma_x z + \frac{1}{2}m_{xy}, \quad \sigma_i^{(1)} z \equiv \frac{1}{2}m_{xy} \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eq. (7) and Eq. (8) into Eq. (10) considering that the bending modes in Fig. 3b are independent for an antiplane core, the following relationships are obtained

$$Q_{33} = 16E_i z_i z, \quad 16Q_{11} z^2 + 8Q_{13} z + Q_{33} = 16E_i (z^2 - z z_i), \quad 4Q_{13} z + Q_{33} = 0, \quad (11)$$

The constitutive terms reduce to

$$Q_{11} = E(z), \quad Q_{22} = G(z), \quad Q_{13} = -4E(z)z_i(z), \quad Q_{33} = 16E(z)z z_i(z) \quad (12)$$

where Q_{22} is obtained following the same reasoning as in the conventional Timoshenko beam theory. Substituting Q_{ij} back into Eq. (7) and further into Eq. (3) the following relations between resultants and strains are obtained

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M_0 \\ Q_0 \\ M_l \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B & 0 & 0 \\ B & D_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_Q & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & D_l \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \\ \kappa_\phi \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where $D_0 = D_g - D_l$. The axial A , bending D_g, D_l , axial-bending B and transverse shear D_Q terms of a unit-width sandwich beam with antiplane core are given by

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} E(z) dz, & B &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} E(z) z_i^0 dz = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} E(z) z dz, \\ D_g &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} E(z) z^2 dz, & D_l &= k_m \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} E(z) z z_i(z) dz, & D_Q &= k_s \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} G(z) dz \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where A, B, D_g, D_Q are equal to the terms in the conventional Timoshenko beam theory, while D_l is the additional term due to the local cell bending stiffness. The terms A, B, D_g, D_l are integrated over the sandwich faces only, whereas D_Q includes the core. The coefficient k_m is introduced to describe a non-uniform distribution of couple stresses over the depth for $(EI)_t \neq (EI)_b$.

2.2.2. Complete model

Let us consider an extension of Eq. (13) in which the core can have non-negligible normal and couple stress contribution, $\sigma_c \neq 0$. The core can induce coupling between the modes shown in Fig. 3b, here described through the additional parameters $C_{14} = C_{41} = C_1$ and $C_{24} = C_{42} = C_2$. The extended constitutive matrix is given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M_0 \\ Q_0 \\ M_l \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B & 0 & C_1 \\ B & D_0 & 0 & C_2 \\ 0 & 0 & D_Q & 0 \\ C_1 & C_2 & 0 & D_l \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \\ \kappa_\phi \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The terms A, B, D_g, D_l have similar physical meaning as in Eq. (13) but now include the core stiffness contribution. Micromechanical analysis is utilized next to determine the parameters in Eq. (15) and demonstrate their physical meaning with respect to the deformation of a unit cell.

3. Micromechanical approach for periodic sandwich structures

Let us define an unit-cell approach to determine stiffness terms for periodic sandwich beams. Consider a periodic cell following the conventions of Fig. 3a in the local coordinate system, whose origin is at the cell mid-length and mid-depth. Boundary displacements are applied to the corner nodes inducing deformation modes Δ , which are utilized to determine the constitutive terms in Eq. (15) for a unit-width sandwich beam with arbitrary periodic core.

Figure 4: Displacement boundary conditions used in the micromechanical approach for stiffness computation.

3.1. Axial, bending and coupling terms

Figures 4a-b show idealized strain cases that involve periodic axial translation of the sandwich corners. The displacement boundary conditions that define Δ_1 and Δ_2 are

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1 : \quad u^\Gamma &= u^l\left(\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right) = -u^l\left(-\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right), \quad \theta^l\left(\pm \frac{s}{2}, z^l\right) = 0 \\ \Delta_2 : \quad u^\Gamma &= u^l\left(\frac{s}{2}, \frac{d}{2}\right) = -u^l\left(\frac{s}{2}, -\frac{d}{2}\right), \quad u^l\left(\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right) = -u^l\left(-\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right), \quad \theta^l\left(\pm \frac{s}{2}, z^l\right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and corresponding strains

$$\Delta_1 : \quad \epsilon_0 = \frac{2u^\Gamma}{s}, \quad \Delta_2 : \quad \kappa_\phi = \frac{4u^\Gamma}{sd} \quad (17)$$

Based on the conventions of Fig. 2, the stress resultants are obtained (Fig. 4a)

$$N = N_t + N_b, \quad M_0 = (N_t - N_b)\frac{d}{2}, \quad M_l = M_t + M_b \quad (18)$$

The combinations that define the axial, bending and coupling stiffness terms become

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1 : \quad A &= \frac{N}{\epsilon_0} = \frac{(N_t + N_b)s}{2u^\Gamma}, \quad B = \frac{M_0}{\epsilon_0} = \frac{(N_t - N_b)sd}{4u^\Gamma}, \quad C_1 = \frac{M_l}{\epsilon_0} = \frac{(M_t + M_b)s}{2u^\Gamma} \\ \Delta_2 : \quad B &= \frac{N}{\kappa_\phi} = \frac{(N_t + N_b)sd}{4u^\Gamma}, \quad D_0 = \frac{M_0}{\kappa_\phi} = \frac{(N_t - N_b)sd^2}{8u^\Gamma}, \quad C_2 = \frac{M_l}{\kappa_\phi} = \frac{(M_t + M_b)sd}{4u^\Gamma} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

which for the antiplane core assumption of section 2.2.1 reduce to

$$A = E_t t_t + E_b t_b, \quad B = \frac{(E_t t_t - E_b t_b)d}{2}, \quad D_0 = \frac{(E_t t_t + E_b t_b)d^2}{4}, \quad C_1 = C_2 = 0 \quad (20)$$

where E_t, E_b and t_t, t_b are, respectively, the elastic moduli and thickness of top and bottom faces.

3.2. Transverse shear stiffness

Consider in Fig. 4c a sandwich cell under periodic transverse shear deformation. The boundary conditions that define this mode are given by

$$\begin{aligned} w^\Gamma &= w^l\left(\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right) = -w^l\left(-\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right), \quad u^l\left(\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right) = u^l\left(-\frac{s}{2}, z^l\right), \\ N\left(\frac{s}{2}, \frac{d}{2}\right) &= N\left(-\frac{s}{2}, -\frac{d}{2}\right) = -N\left(\frac{s}{2}, -\frac{d}{2}\right) = -N\left(-\frac{s}{2}, \frac{d}{2}\right) = \frac{(V_t + V_b)s}{2d} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The equivalent transverse shear strain and resultant Q_0 are given by

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{2w^\Gamma}{s} + \frac{1}{d} \left[u^l \left(\frac{s}{2}, \frac{d}{2} \right) - u^l \left(\frac{s}{2}, -\frac{d}{2} \right) \right], \quad Q_0 = V_t + V_b, \quad (22)$$

whose quotient defines D_Q

$$D_Q = \frac{Q_0}{\gamma_{xz}} = \frac{(V_t + V_b)sd}{2w^\Gamma d + \left[u^l \left(\frac{s}{2}, \frac{d}{2} \right) - u^l \left(\frac{s}{2}, -\frac{d}{2} \right) \right] s} \quad (23)$$

3.3. Local bending and coupling terms

Figure 4d shows a unit cell bending to a constant slope at each boundary. The displacement boundary conditions and resulting curvature that define Δ_4 are given by

$$\theta^\Gamma = \theta^l \left(\frac{s}{2}, z^l \right) = -\theta^l \left(-\frac{s}{2}, z^l \right), \quad u^l \left(\pm \frac{s}{2}, z^l \right) = 0, \quad \kappa = \frac{2\theta^\Gamma}{s} \quad (24)$$

and the stress resultants are shown in Eq. (18). The local bending term D_l is defined

$$D_l = \frac{(M_t + M_b)s}{2\theta^\Gamma}, \quad C_1 = \frac{(N_t + N_b)s}{2\theta^\Gamma}, \quad C_2 = \frac{(N_t - N_b)sd}{4\theta^\Gamma}, \quad (25)$$

where the coupling terms result equal to those determined in Eq. (19). For an antiplane core, Eq. (25) reduces to

$$D_l = \frac{E_t t_t^3 + E_b t_b^3}{12}, \quad C_1 = C_2 = 0 \quad (26)$$

4. Analysis of selected periodic sandwich beams

Figure 5 shows the unit cells of selected periodic sandwich beams discretized with linear elastic Euler-Bernoulli frame elements. The web-core (Fig. 5a) has semi-rigid joints as result of the laser-welding process [45], while the triangular core (Fig. 5b) and X-core (Fig. 5c) cells are assumed to be continuous entities [3, 7]. For the selected cells, the material properties are equal for all elements, described by the elastic constants E and ν . The faces have thickness $t_t = t_b = t_f$, while the core members have thickness t_c .

Figure 5: Conventions used in the analysis of (a) web-core (b) triangular core (c) X-core cells.

4.1. Constitutive terms

The stiffness terms of Eq. (15) are determined by enforcing the displacement conditions of the micromechanical approach to nodes 1-4, evaluating the boundary resultants and computing the relations of Eqs. (19), (23) and (25). Additional boundary conditions needed to prevent rigid-body motion are assigned to node 5. Closed-form stiffness relations are given next for the selected cases.

4.1.1. Laser-welded web-core sandwich beam (Fig. 5a)

For the web-core, the antiplane core assumption is valid exactly. Thus, Eq. (14) provides the same axial, bending and coupling stiffness parameters as in the micromechanical approach

$$A = 2Et_f, \quad B = C_1 = C_2 = 0, \quad D_0 = \frac{Et_f d^2}{2}, \quad D_l = \frac{Et_f^3}{6} \quad (27)$$

The transverse shear stiffness D_Q [32] is given by

$$D_Q = \frac{2Ed^2 t_f^3 t_c^3}{s(k_1 t_f^3 t_c^3 d^2 + 2d^3 t_f^3 + s t_c^3 (d^2 + t_f^2))}, \quad k_1 = \frac{E}{k_\theta} \quad (28)$$

with k_θ as the face-core connection rotational stiffness.

4.1.2. Triangular core sandwich beam (Fig. 5b)

The axial, bending and coupling stiffness terms of the triangular core cell are

$$A = 2Et_f + A_c, \quad B = -C_1 = -\frac{A_c d}{2}, \quad D_0 = \frac{Et_f d^2}{2} + \frac{A_c d^2}{4}, \quad D_l = \frac{Et_f^3}{6} + \frac{Ect_c^3}{3p}, \quad C_2 = -\frac{A_c d^2}{4} \quad (29)$$

The core-dependent term A_c and transverse shear stiffness D_Q [36] are

$$A_c = \frac{E p c t_c^3}{d^2 p^2 + c^2 t_c^2}, \quad D_Q = \frac{E c d^2 t_f t_c}{p^3 t_f + c^3 t_c} \quad (30)$$

4.1.3. X-core sandwich beam (Fig. 5c)

For the X-core cell, the axial, bending and coupling stiffness terms result

$$A = 2Et_f + A_c, \quad B = -C_1 = 0, \quad D_0 = \frac{Et_f d^2}{2} + \frac{A_c d^2}{4}, \quad D_l = \frac{Et_f^3}{6} + \frac{E s t_c^3}{3p}, \quad C_2 = -\frac{A_c d^2}{8} \quad (31)$$

The core-dependent term A_c and transverse shear stiffness D_Q [36] are

$$A_c = \frac{4E s p t_c^3}{d^2 p^2 + s^2 t_c^2}, \quad D_Q = \frac{E s d^2 t_c}{4p^3} \quad (32)$$

4.2. Linear stress localization

Let us define a face stress localization scheme for sandwich beams with cells shown in Fig. 5. The present analysis concerns linear elastic bending; the axial degree of freedom is removed. The beam continuum solution is averaged for $n = 1..N$ cells to describe normal and bending resultants at $k = 1..K$ intervals of $i = t, b$ faces (Fig. 6)

$$N_i^k = \frac{1}{s} \int_{(n-1)s+s_i}^{ns+s_i} \frac{M_0}{d_i} dx, \quad (33)$$

$$M_i^k(x_i^k) = \frac{k_l}{s} \int_{(n-1)s+s_i}^{ns+s_i} M_l dx + \frac{x_i^k}{s} \int_{(n-1)s+s_i}^{ns+s_i} (k_Q^0 Q_0 + k_Q^l Q_l) dx,$$

where $-s/2 \leq x_i^k \leq s/2$, $d_t = d/2$ and $d_b = -d/2$. Under the cell conventions of Fig. 6a-b, $k \equiv n$ and $s_t = s_b = 0$ for web- and X-core, whereas for the triangular core, $s_b = 0$ and $s_t = s/2$ (Fig. 6c).

The triangular core has an incomplete segment near the beam boundaries ($k = 1, k = K$), which must be treated as a special case. Equation (33) relies on the factors k_Q^0, k_Q^l and k_l to predict the bending stress distribution over the cross-section height. In the present work we assume $k_Q^l = k_l$, where k_l describes the relative face bending stiffness with respect to the cell average. The factor k_Q^0 distributes the global shear according to Section 3.2. For the cores under study, the following factors are obtained

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Web-core: } k_l &= k_Q^0 = \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{Triangular core: } k_l &= \frac{pt_f^3}{2pt_f^3 + ct_c^3}, \quad k_Q^0 = \frac{p^2t_f^3t_c^2}{2(c^2p^2 + d^2t_c^2)t_f^3 + 4pc^3t_c^3} \\
\text{X-core: } k_l &= \frac{pt_f^3}{2pt_f^3 + st_c^3}, \quad k_Q^0 = \frac{2p^2t_f^3t_c^2}{(4s^2p^2 + d^2t_c^2)t_f^3 + 2ps^3t_c^3}
\end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

The total stress at the sandwich face i within segment k is given by

$$\sigma_i^k(x_i^k, z_i) = \frac{N_i^k}{t_f} + \frac{12M_i^k z_i}{t_f^3} \tag{35}$$

where z_i is the local face coordinate (see Fig. 3b).

Figure 6: Stress analysis conventions illustrated for (a) X-core (b) web-core (c) triangular core sandwich beams.

5. Equivalence between present model and thick-face sandwich theory

5.1. Thick-face sandwich beam theory

We revise the thick-face sandwich beam theory according to the conceptual framework of Allen [10] and Plantema [11]. In their works, the effect of thick faces is included by studying the shear deformation compatibility between core and faces. The global sandwich beam response is defined

$$q_1 = -\frac{\partial Q_1}{\partial x}, \quad Q_1 = \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial x}, \quad M_1 = -D_g \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x^2} \tag{36}$$

Near discontinuities, the faces must bend to a finite curvature for faces and core to remain attached. Thus, they are locally subjected to a set of loads, shear forces and bending moments

$$q_2 = -\frac{\partial Q_2}{\partial x}, \quad Q_2 = \frac{\partial M_2}{\partial x}, \quad M_2 = -D_f \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial x^2} \tag{37}$$

The corresponding total quantities are given by

$$q = q_1 + q_2, \quad Q = Q_1 + Q_2, \quad M = M_1 + M_2, \quad w = w_1 + w_2 \quad (38)$$

Shear strain compatibility between face and core results in the following relations

$$-Q_1 = D_g \frac{\partial^3 w_1}{\partial x^3} = -D_Q \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial x} + D_f \frac{\partial^3 w_1}{\partial x^3} \quad (39)$$

which after some rearranging becomes

$$\frac{\partial^2 Q_1}{\partial x^2} - a^2 Q_1 = -a^2 Q, \quad a^2 = \frac{D_Q D_g}{D_f D_0} \quad (40)$$

5.2. Equivalence between models

Let us introduce some general assumptions to study the equivalence between the thick-face sandwich theory and the couple stress sandwich model

- The axial degree of freedom u of the couple stress beam is removed;
- The sandwich beam has an antiplane core;
- Horizontal sliding, denoted γ_0 in Allen [10], is excluded from the analyses;

as a result of the first assumption, the equilibrium equations of the couple stress beam result

$$\frac{\partial Q_0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_l}{\partial x} - q = 0, \quad Q_0 - \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (41)$$

Based on the second assumption and considering the faces to be equal, we obtain the following common stiffness terms for both, thick-face and couple stress sandwich models

$$D_0 = \frac{E_f t_f d^2}{2}, \quad D_l = D_f = 2E_f I_f, \quad D_g = D_0 + D_l \quad (42)$$

We shall now proceed with the equivalency derivations, which are developed for the static bending case. Substituting the relations in Eq. (13) into Eq. (41b), we obtain a relation between shear angle and cross-sectional rotation angle

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{D_0}{D_Q} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} \quad (43)$$

Writing Eq. (41a) in terms of displacements, and substituting the shear angle definition of Eq. (2b)

$$q = D_g \frac{\partial^3 \phi}{\partial x^3} - D_f \frac{\partial^3 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x^3} \quad (44)$$

Integrating Eq. (41a) and defining $\int q dx = Q$, we obtain

$$Q = D_g \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} - D_f \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x^2} + C = Q_g + Q_l^\gamma \quad (45)$$

where the constant of integration obtained is included in Q_g . We now substitute Q_g into Eq. (43) and differentiate twice

$$\frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x^2} = \frac{D_0}{D_Q D_g} \frac{\partial^2 Q_g}{\partial x^2} \quad (46)$$

Isolating $\frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x^2}$ in Eq. (45) and substituting in Eq. (46), the following differential equation is obtained

$$\frac{D_f D_0}{D_g D_Q} \frac{\partial^2 Q_g}{\partial x^2} = -Q + Q_g \rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 Q_g}{\partial x^2} - a^2 Q_g = -a^2 Q, \quad a^2 = \frac{D_Q D_g}{D_f D_0} \quad (47)$$

Eq. (47) is equal to the governing equation of the thick-face sandwich theory, Eq. (40), acknowledging that $Q_g = Q_1$. Therefore, the two theories are shown to be equivalent for the basic assumptions of [10].

6. Finite element model

Consider in Fig. 7 the finite element of length l_e and height h_e as proposed in [25], which is utilized to solve the equilibrium equations in the present work. The element is re-worked for the stress resultant definitions of Eq. (3) and constitutive matrix of Eq. (15), resulting in a different elemental stiffness matrix than the one presented in [25]. The element has two nodes and four degrees of freedom per node

$$\mathbf{u}^e = \{u_1 \ \phi_1 \ w_1 \ \theta_1 \ u_2 \ \phi_2 \ w_2 \ \theta_2\}^T \quad (48)$$

with positive directions following the conventions in Fig. 2. The primary variables u and ϕ are approximated using Lagrange linear polynomials ψ_i , while w and θ are approximated using Hermitian cubic polynomials φ_i [25]

$$u(x) = \sum_{i=1}^2 u_i \psi_i, \quad \phi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \phi_i \psi_i, \quad w(x) = \sum_{i=1}^4 \bar{\Delta}_i \varphi_i \quad (49)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} u_1 &= u(0), & u_2 &= u(l_e), & \phi_1 &= \phi(0), & \phi_2 &= \phi(l_e) \\ \bar{\Delta}_1 &= w(0), & \bar{\Delta}_2 &= \theta(0), & \bar{\Delta}_3 &= w(l_e), & \bar{\Delta}_4 &= \theta(l_e), \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

The stress resultants at the nodes are determined in relation to the positive directions of Fig. 2

$$\begin{aligned} N_1 &= -N(0), & \bar{Q}_1 &= -\bar{Q}(0), & M_{0,1} &= -M_0(0), & M_{l,1} &= -M_l(0) \\ N_2 &= N(l_e), & \bar{Q}_2 &= \bar{Q}(l_e), & M_{0,2} &= M_0(l_e), & M_{l,2} &= M_l(l_e) \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

We present next the finite element equations for linear, geometric nonlinear and eigenvalue buckling analyses.

6.1. Linear finite element equations

The linear finite element equations arise from removing the *von Kármán* term from the axial strain description. In this case, the elemental stiffness matrix becomes

$$\mathbf{K}^e = \int_0^{l_e} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} \, dx \quad (52)$$

where $\mathbf{B}$ (Eq. (A.1)) is the linear strain-displacement matrix and $\mathbf{C}$ is the constitutive matrix in Eq. (15). The standard finite element equations $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u}$ are then solved after assembling the elements and enforcing the loads and boundary conditions.

Figure 7: Two-node beam element for the couple stress sandwich beam model [25].

6.2. Nonlinear finite element equations

Let us now consider the *von Kármán* nonlinear problem. In an analogy with Eq. (52), the updated finite element equations become [46, 47]

$$\mathbf{K}^e = \int_0^{l_e} (\mathbf{B} + \theta \mathbf{B}_\sigma)^T \mathbf{C} (\mathbf{B} + \frac{\theta}{2} \mathbf{B}_\sigma) dx \quad (53)$$

where $\mathbf{B}_\sigma$ is defined in Eq. (A.2). In short, the objective is to minimize the residual

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{u})\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{F} \quad (54)$$

using a solution procedure for nonlinear differential equations such as the Newton-Raphson method. The tangent stiffness matrix derivations follow the standard steps as in [48].

6.3. Linear buckling analysis

Let us now consider the eigenvalue elastic buckling problem. Assume that the beam is subjected to a constant axial force P that induces transverse displacements. Following the basic steps in [49], the geometric stiffness matrix becomes

$$\mathbf{K}_\sigma^e = \int_0^{l_e} P \mathbf{B}_\sigma^T \mathbf{B}_\sigma dx \quad (55)$$

The conventional eigenvalue buckling problem is then solved upon assembling the global matrices

$$(\mathbf{K} - \lambda \mathbf{K}_\sigma) \mathbf{d}_\sigma = 0 \quad (56)$$

where the eigenvalues λ correspond to the buckling loads and the eigenvector $\mathbf{d}_\sigma$ provides the buckling modes.

7. Numerical results

7.1. General assumptions

In order to demonstrate the present model, we study the linear and geometric nonlinear response of elastic periodic sandwich beams. In the following analyses, the beams represent wide panels along the y -axis, whose response is two-dimensional. Plane strain conditions are then assumed, with elastic modulus set to $E = E_s / (1 - \nu_s^2)$. The following material properties are taken for faces and core in all cases: $E_s = 206$ GPa and $\nu_s = 0.3$. The results are shown for a unit-width beam, $b = 1.0$ m. The examples are validated using finite element models that represent the 3-D geometry

Figure 8: (a) Example of three-dimensional model as used for validation. (b) Boundary conditions utilized in the 3-D FE validation models of section 7.2 (Table 1) for different cell setups.

Figure 9: Unit cell models of (a) truss-core (b) Y-frame core sandwich beams as utilized in Sections 7.2 and 7.5.

(3-D FE), constructed with Abaqus S4R shell elements as illustrated in Fig. 8a. The constitutive model of Section 2.2.2 with stiffness terms derived as in Sections 3 and 4 is utilized to compute the responses. In the following analyses, relative error is defined with respect to an equivalent 3-D FE model

$$\bar{E}(\%) = 100 \left(\frac{w_m - w_{(3-D)}}{w_{(3-D)}} \right) \quad (57)$$

where m refers to the model at hand.

7.2. Linear deflection analyses: truss-core sandwich beams

In the first case, we study the linear bending response of sandwich beams composed of truss-core cells of length $s = 4a + 2c = 0.2\text{ m}$ (Fig. 9a). Setup A is the same as two web-core cells with rigid joints, $k_\theta \rightarrow \infty$ (stiffness terms in Section 4.1.1), while closed-form stiffness terms for setup C are shown in Section 4.1.2. Table 1 summarizes the core geometries under investigation. The boundary conditions utilized in the validation models are shown in Fig. 8b.

7.2.1. Validation

Deflections obtained with the present model are compared to the validation models in Table 1 for a 2.0 m beam with $d/t_c = 20$ under three-point bending ($F = 10\text{ kN}$). The results are also validated against the closed-form thick-face sandwich theory solution presented in [10]. Overall, very good predictions are obtained in all cases. The present model predicts the same deflections as the thick-face sandwich theory for the antiplane setup A, validating the derivations in 5.2. Minor differences are seen in setups B and C due to face-core interactions, which are neglected in [10] while included in the present constitutive equations; the present model is slightly stiffer than [10].

Table 1: Cell setups, dimensions, corresponding stiffness parameters and maximum deflections predicted with present and validation models for $L = 2.0$ m beams under three-point bending ($F = 10$ kN).

Periodic sandwich cells			Constitutive terms				Max. deflection, w_{max} [mm]			
Setup	Core	t_f/t_c s/d	D_0 [kNm]	D_l [kNm]	C_2 [kNm]	D_Q [kN/m]	3-D FE	Sandwich theory [10]	Present	
A.1		2	2	11318.7	37.7	0	2661.65	1.804	1.791	1.791 (-0.7%)
A.2		4	4	1414.84	4.72	0	628.118	8.400	8.398	8.398 (0.0%)
A.3		1	2	5659.34	4.72	0	1884.88	2.843	2.810	2.810 (-1.1%)
A.4		4	4	707.418	0.590	0	353.267	16.053	15.907	15.907 (-0.9%)
A.5		2	2	2829.67	0.59	0	565.651	9.337	9.139	9.139 (-2.1%)
A.6		0.5	4	353.709	0.074	0	78.5583	67.826	66.383	66.383 (-2.1%)
B.1		2	2	11324.2	43.9	-5.5	37311.7	0.277	0.276	0.275 (-0.8%)
B.2		4	4	1416.01	5.93	-1.18	1318.12	4.678	4.717	4.689 (0.2%)
B.3		1	2	5662.62	8.53	-3.28	11455.5	0.714	0.721	0.718 (0.6%)
B.4		4	4	707.870	1.066	-0.453	543.032	11.089	11.244	11.138 (0.4%)
B.5		2	2	2830.44	1.57	-0.77	3462.50	1.970	2.013	2.001 (1.6%)
B.6		0.5	4	353.785	0.156	-0.079	124.647	42.753	43.833	43.389 (1.5%)
C.1		2	2	11323.7	44.4	-5.0	340061	0.160	0.161	0.161 (0.8%)
C.2		4	4	1415.62	5.77	-0.79	74561.4	1.229	1.240	1.240 (0.9%)
C.3		1	2	5664.34	11.39	-5.00	295648	0.308	0.311	0.311 (0.9%)
C.4		4	4	708.207	1.644	-0.789	59011.9	2.414	2.438	2.437 (1.0%)
C.5		2	2	2834.67	7.26	-5.00	234418	0.604	0.610	0.610 (1.0%)
C.6		0.5	4	354.498	1.128	-0.789	41642.9	4.780	4.831	4.827 (1.0%)

Figure 10: Relative error in the three-point bending analysis of truss-core beams with parameters $n_c/\alpha/d/t_c$ (α in $^\circ$, t_c, d in [mm]) using different models as function of the scale parameter Δ , and corresponding shear-flexibility parameter Θ for each setup.

7.2.2. Size effect analyses

We extend the example to study the size-dependent response of periodic sandwich beams as function of their shear flexibility $D_Q L^2$. In the following analyses, the suitability of classical and couple stress models to predict maximum deflections is also investigated. Let us consider truss-core beams with $s = 0.2$ m, $s/t_f = 25$ and varying core thickness t_c , depth d and corrugation angle α , under three-point bending. The beams also have different amount of cells, $n_c = L/s$. The following

measures Δ and Θ are used to quantify shear flexibility and scale coupling sensitivity [12, 36]

$$\Delta = \left(\frac{D_l + C_2}{D_Q L^2} \right)^{0.5}, \quad \Theta = \left(\frac{D_0 + C_2}{D_Q L^2} \right)^{0.5} \quad (58)$$

Results are shown in Figure 10 for selected cores with varying parameter combinations denoted $n_c/\alpha/d/t_c$, where α is shown in $[\circ]$ and d, t_c in $[\text{mm}]$. Overall, it is shown that the present model outputs accurate predictions for all Θ and Δ . The classical Timoshenko model is accurate when $\Delta \approx 0$ and $C_2, D_l \ll D_0$. In general words, its error typically becomes relevant in relatively short beams composed of cells with low-density cores, and whose shear-carrying mechanism is primarily through bending. The model in [30] is only accurate when $\Theta \approx 0$ and $C_2 \ll D_0$, a much more restrictive requirement in light of the typical periodic sandwich construction.

Figure 11: Deflection along the beam length for (a) Case I: web-core (b) Case II: triangular core (c) Case III: X-core (Section 8.3).

Figure 12: Bottom surface (linear) stress distribution at the bottom face of simply-supported web-core sandwich beam ($F = -10$ kN at $x = L/2$) with cell parameters $d = 0.05$ m, $s = 0.1$ m, $t_f = t_c = 0.004$ m, $k_\theta = 100$ kN (Case I).

Figure 13: Bottom surface (linear) stress distribution at the bottom face of cantilevered triangular core sandwich beam ($F = -50$ kN at $x = L$) with cell parameters $d = 0.1$ m, $c = 0.1$ m, $t_f = 0.006$ m, $t_c = 0.003$ (Case II).

Figure 14: Bottom surface (linear) stress distribution at the bottom face of doubly-clamped X-core sandwich beam ($F = -500$ kN at $x = L/2$) with cell parameters $d = 0.1$ m, $s = 0.1$ m, $t_f = 0.008$ m, $t_c = 0.003$ (Case III).

7.3. Linear stress analysis: web-core, triangular core and X-core

Let us employ next the localization scheme of Section 4.2 to predict the face stress distribution of selected periodic sandwich beams with relatively few cells. Case I concerns a web-core beam with dimensions (Fig. 5a) $d = 0.05$ m, $s = 0.1$ m, $t_f = t_c = 0.004$ m, semi-rigid joints with $k_\theta = 100$ kN and overall length $L = 0.8$ m in three-point bending, $F = -10$ kN at $x = L/2$. Case II is a triangular core cantilever, $F = -50$ kN at the free end, $x = L$; the cell dimensions are (Fig. 5b) $d = 0.1$ m, $c = 0.1$ m, $t_f = 0.006$ m, $t_c = 0.003$ m and beam length $L = 1.6$ m. Case III concerns a doubly-clamped X-core beam with $F = -500$ kN at $x = L/2$; the cell dimensions are (Fig. 5c) $d = 0.1$ m, $s = 0.1$ m, $t_f = 0.008$ m, $t_c = 0.003$ m, and overall length $L = 1.2$ m.

Figure 11 shows the deflection plots, whereas Figs. 12-14 show the stress distribution at the bottom surface ($z_i = -t_f/2$) of the bottom face of each beam. Overall, good agreement between

present and validation models is observed. Membrane and bending stress components are also isolated in the stress plots. In Fig. 12, the web-core is flexible and bending stresses (shear-induced and local) are dominant. The cores in Figs. 13-14 are stiffer due to their stretch-dominated mechanism. As result, the sandwich effect is stronger and stresses at the faces arise primarily from the membrane action. In Figs. 13-14, the effect of local boundary conditions in the shear distribution is superimposed to the beam solution through a local correction. An auxiliary shear model with $w^\Gamma = w^l(s/2, z^l) = -w^l(-s/2, z^l)$, $u^l(\pm s/2, z^l) = 0$ and $\theta^l(-s/2, z^l) = 0$ is utilized to predict the shear force shared by the first face segment near the boundary and point force, where the slope is restricted at one end. A shear distribution factor is estimated for $\bar{Q} = Q_0 + Q_l$ based on this model. We assume the boundary effect to vanish after the nearest face-core hard point.

Figure 15: Unit cell models utilized to estimate the shear response near global boundary conditions (a) triangular core (b) X-core.

7.4. Nonlinear bending analysis: web-core sandwich beams

Consider a web-core unit cell with dimensions $s = 0.12$ m, $d = 0.0435$ m, $t_f = 0.003$ m and $t_c = 0.004$ m (see Fig. 5a). The cell has semi-rigid joints, whose rotational stiffness is half of the average reported in [45], $k_\theta = 53.5$ kN. A sandwich beam composed of 10 of such cells ($L = 1.2$ m) is subjected to nonlinear bending. Two doubly-clamped settings are investigated, where the load is either concentrated at the mid-length, or distributed over the top face plate. The Newton-Raphson algorithm is utilized in conjunction with the finite element method to obtain an approximate solution to the nonlinear equilibrium equations. The convergence tolerance is set to 10^{-4} and the analysis is divided into fine load steps. Figure 16 shows the load vs. maximum deflection relations in either case, as well as comparisons with the conventional Timoshenko beam and validation model. Overall, the couple stress sandwich model satisfactorily predicts the nonlinear response in terms of displacements. In the linear range, a slight error (4-5%) related to the global shear description of the couple stress model is observed. The example under consideration is an extreme case with relatively few, highly shear-flexible cells. More involved models, such as the micropolar theory [37], can be used in such case for a more precise response prediction. The error is rapidly reduced as the geometric nonlinearity increases and the membrane action becomes dominant. In both cases, the couple stress sandwich model is considerably more accurate than the conventional Timoshenko beam theory with effective properties.

7.5. Elastic buckling analysis: Y-frame core sandwich beams

Take a unit cell of a Y-frame core sandwich beam with similar dimensions as in [5], namely $a = 0.002$ m, $d_1 = 0.013$ m, $d = 0.022$ m, $s = 0.026$ m, $t_f = 0.001$ m and $t_c = 0.0003$ m (Fig. 9b).

Figure 16: Nonlinear bending analysis of clamped web-core sandwich beams with cell parameters $s = 0.12$ m, $d = 0.0435$ m, $t_f = 0.003$ m and $t_c = 0.004$ m under (a) centered point force (b) distributed load.

Y-frame structures used in ship design are often composed of relatively few cells, thus prone to size effects, which we investigate next. We analyze the changes in linear buckling loads of axially compressed Y-frame beams as function of their relative unit-cell size s/L . Two configurations are covered, namely an end-loaded cantilever and a pinned-pinned beam loaded at both ends. Figure 17 shows the buckling load predicted with the validation models and the relative errors obtained with classical Timoshenko and couple stress sandwich models. Overall, the conventional Timoshenko model is progressively less accurate as the cell size approaches the total structural length. This supports the observations in [32, 36], where a conventional couple stress model was used to model the sandwich structures. The present model succeeds in describing size effects in Y-frame core sandwich structures, displaying very good accuracy against the validation models.

Figure 17: Elastic buckling load and relative errors in the analysis of end-loaded Y-frame sandwich beams with cell parameters $a = 0.002$ m, $d_1 = 0.013$ m, $d = 0.022$ m, $s = 0.026$ m, $t_f = 0.001$ m, $t_c = 0.0003$ m and (a) clamped-free (b) simply-supported boundary conditions.

8. Conclusions

A couple stress model for the analysis of periodic sandwich beams was established and demonstrated for different cores. Constitutive relations for the modified couple stress Timoshenko beam theory were derived assuming an antiplane core and then extended for a generic periodic sandwich cell. The complete constitutive matrix has couplings between membrane resultant and local curvature, and boundary moment and axial strain, which are induced by the core. A micromechanical approach was proposed as a generalization of previous works (e.g. [3, 36, 50, 51]), and applied to determine effective stiffness properties of selected beams. A face stress recovery scheme for these beams was then defined. The present sandwich model was shown to be equivalent to the thick-face sandwich theory in the linear case [10–12] for the same basic assumptions such as an antiplane core. Validation in linear bending was provided in comparison with three-dimensional finite element models and the thick-face sandwich theory. The significance of a couple stress shear-deformable model was clarified by studying the size-dependent bending response of sandwich beams and contrasting it with the couple stress Euler-Bernoulli [30] and the classical Timoshenko model. The present model was also validated in linear buckling and geometrically nonlinear bending, where the *von Kármán* assumption was shown suitable to predict geometric nonlinearities at the global structural scale. The present model is not able to describe local geometric nonlinearities such as local buckling. A multiscale framework to capture local buckling in periodic sandwich beams will be presented in a future publication.

Overall, the present model was shown to successfully describe the elastic response of periodic sandwich beams. The stress recovery scheme predicts stresses accurately using simple unit cell averaging and height-distribution factors for the global shear and local components. The stress distributions have a predictor-level accuracy and do not strictly guarantee equilibrium or energy conservation between scales, for which a corrector phase could be utilized. Near shear discontinuities, such as point forces and clamped boundary conditions, the local boundary conditions influence the shear force distribution. In the present work, we utilize an auxiliary shear model to predict the total shear distribution at the face segments connected to the beam boundaries, obtaining improved accuracy against the validation models while locally affecting the micro-macro energy equivalence.

Contrary to the conventional Timoshenko beam, the present model is able to predict stiffness near shear discontinuities and describe size effects present in short, shear-flexible structures. Unlike the general constitutive model for layered structures shown in [23, 25], the present model allows the description of face-core stiffness interactions via coupling constitutive terms. We note that the present model includes information up to the second derivative of displacement; a more accurate model shall result if higher-order derivatives are to be included, at the cost of a more involved formulation. The present model is also based on a single shear stiffness description for horizontal and vertical global shear, which may result in slight deviations in extremely shear-flexible cores [37]. Finally, we note that the couple stress model herein introduced is aimed for the description of sandwich beams with discrete, periodic cells, and not macroscopically continuous sandwich beams with length-scale interactions as in [52, 53].

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Appendix A. Finite element matrices

The elemental matrices needed for the finite element computations are given as follows. The linear strain-displacement matrix $\mathbf{B}$ that approximates the relations between nodal displacements (Eq. (48)) and linear strains of the couple stress sandwich model is given by

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \psi'_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi'_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \psi'_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi'_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \psi_1 & \varphi'_1 & -\varphi'_2 & 0 & \psi_2 & \varphi'_3 & -\varphi'_4 \\ 0 & 0 & -\varphi''_1 & \varphi''_2 & 0 & 0 & -\varphi''_3 & \varphi''_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The geometric strain-displacement matrix, which interpolates the *von Kármán* nonlinear terms, is given by

$$\mathbf{B}_\sigma = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -\varphi'_1 & \varphi'_2 & 0 & 0 & -\varphi'_3 & \varphi'_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

References

- [1] C. A. Steeves, N. A. Fleck, Material selection in sandwich beam construction, *Scripta Materialia* 50 (2004) 1335–1339.
- [2] N. Fleck, V. Deshpande, M. Ashby, Micro-architected materials: past, present and future, *Proc. R. Soc. A* 466 (2010) 2495–2516.
- [3] T.-S. Lok, Q.-H. Cheng, Elastic stiffness properties and behavior of truss-core sandwich panel, *J. Struct. Eng.* 126 (5).
- [4] J. Romanoff, P. Varsta, Stress analysis of homogenized web-core sandwich beams, *Compos. Struct.* 79 (3) (2007) 411–422.
- [5] L. St-Pierre, V. Deshpande, N. Fleck, The low velocity impact response of sandwich beams with a corrugated core or a y-frame core, *Compos. Struct.* 91 (2015) 71–80.
- [6] E. Carrera, S. Brischetto, A survey with numerical assessment of classical and refined theories for the analysis of sandwich plates, *Appl. Mech. Rev* 62 (1).
- [7] L. He, Y.-S. Cheng, J. Liu, Precise bending stress analysis of corrugated-core, honeycomb-core and x-core sandwich panels, *Compos. Struct.* 94 (5) (2012) 1656–1668.
- [8] Y. Frostig, M. Baruch, Bending of sandwich beams with transversely flexible cores, *AIAA Journal* 28 (3) (1190) 523–531.
- [9] Buannic, P. N., Cartraud, T. Quesnel, Homogenization of corrugated core sandwich panels, *Compos. Struct.* 59 (3) (2003) 299–312.
- [10] H. G. Allen, *Analysis and Design of Structural Sandwich Panels*, Pergamon Press, 1969.
- [11] F. Plantema, *Sandwich construction: the bending and buckling of sandwich beams, plates and shells*, Wiley, 1966.
- [12] D. Zenkert, *An introduction to sandwich construction*, Emas, 1995.
- [13] J. Romanoff, P. Varsta, Bending response of web-core sandwich plates, *Compos. Struct.* 81 (2007) 292–302.
- [14] J. Jelovica, J. Romanoff, Buckling of sandwich panels with transversely flexible core: Correction of the equivalent single-layer model using thick-faces effect, *J. Sand. Struct. Mat.* 0 (0) (2018) 1–23.

- [15] D. C. C. Lam, F. Yang, A. C. M. Chong, J. Wang, P. Tong, Experiments and theory in strain gradient elasticity, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 51 (8) (2003) 1477–1508.
- [16] J. Lei, Y. He, S. Guo, Z. Li, D. Liu, Size-dependent vibration of nickel cantilever microbeams: Experiment and gradient elasticity, *AIP Advances* 6 (10) (2009) 1477508.
- [17] C. Liebold, W. H. Müller, Comparison of gradient elasticity models for the bending of micromaterials, *Computational Materials Science* 116 (2016) 52–61.
- [18] Z. Li, Y. He, J. Lei, S. Han, S. Guo, D. Liu, Experimental investigation on size-dependent higher-mode vibration of cantilever microbeams, *Microsystem Technologies* (2018) 1–11.
- [19] C. Tang, G. Alici, Evaluation of length-scale effects for mechanical behaviour of micro- and nanocantilevers: I. experimental determination of length-scale factors, *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* 44 (33).
- [20] C. Tang, G. Alici, Evaluation of length-scale effects for mechanical behaviour of micro-and nanocantilevers: II. experimental verification of deflection models using atomic force microscopy, *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* 44 (33).
- [21] F. Yang, A. C. M. Chong, D. C. C. Lam, P. Tong, Couple stress based strain gradient theory for elasticity, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 39 (10) (2002) 2731–2743.
- [22] A. R. Hadjesfandiari, G. F. Dargush, Couple stress theory for solids, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 48 (18) (2011) 2496–2510.
- [23] J. N. Reddy, Microstructure-dependent couple stress theories of functionally graded beams, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 59 (11) (2011) 2382–2399.
- [24] H. M. Ma, X.-L. Gao, J. N. Reddy, A microstructure-dependent Timoshenko beam model based on a modified couple stress theory, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 56 (12) (2008) 3379–3391.
- [25] A. Arbind, J. Reddy, Nonlinear analysis of functionally graded microstructure-dependent beams, *Compos. Struct.* 98 (2013) 272–281.
- [26] M. Asghari, M. H. Kahrobaian, M. T. Ahmadian, A nonlinear Timoshenko beam formulation based on the modified couple stress theory, *Int. J. Eng. Sci.* 48 (12) (2010) 1749–1761.
- [27] M. Asghari, M. Rahaeifard, M. H. Kahrobaian, M. T. Ahmadian, The modified couple stress functionally graded Timoshenko beam formulation, *Mater. Design* 32 (3) (2011) 1435–1443.
- [28] H. M. Ma, X.-L. Gao, J. N. Reddy, A non-classical mindlin plate model based on a modified couple stress theory, *Acta Mechanica* 220 (1-4) (2011) 217–235.
- [29] G. C. Tsiatas, A new kirchhoff plate model based on a modified couple stress theory, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 46 (13) (2009) 2757–2764.
- [30] S. K. Park, X.-L. Gao, Bernoulli-euler beam model based on a modified couple stress theory, *J. Micromech. Microeng.* 16 (2006) 23552359.
- [31] A. T. Karttunen, J. Romanoff, J. Reddy, Exact microstructure-dependent timoshenko beam element, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 111-112 (2016) 35–42.
- [32] B. R. Goncalves, A. T. Karttunen, J. Romanoff, J. N. Reddy, Buckling and free vibration of shear-flexible sandwich beams using a couple-stress-based finite element, *Compos. Struct.* 165 (2017) 233–241.
- [33] A. M. Dehrouyeh-Semnani, A. Bahrami, On size-dependent timoshenko beam element based on modified couple stress theory, *Int. J. Eng. Sci.* 107 (2016) 134–148.
- [34] Z. Li, Y. He, J. Lei, S. Guo, D. Liu, L. Wang, A standard experimental method for determining the material length scale based on modified couple stress theory, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*
- [35] J. Romanoff, J. N. Reddy, Experimental validation of the modified couple stress Timoshenko beam theory for web-core sandwich panels, *Compos. Struct.* 111 (2014) 130–137.
- [36] B. R. Goncalves, J. Romanoff, Size-dependent modelling of elastic sandwich beams with prismatic cores, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 136-137 (2018) 28–37.
- [37] A. T. Karttunen, J. N. Reddy, J. Romanoff, Micropolar modeling approach for periodic sandwich beams, *Compos. Struct.* 185 (2018) 656–664.
- [38] S. K. Park, X.-L. Gao, Micromechanical modeling of honeycomb structures based on a modified couple stress theory, *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures* 15 (8) (2008) 574–593.
- [39] S. Liu, W. Su, Effective couple-stress continuum model of cellular solids and size effects analysis, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 46 (14-15) (2009) 2787–2799.
- [40] A. K. Noor, M. P. Nemeth, Micropolar beam models for lattice grids with rigid joints, *Comput. Meth. Appl. Mech. Eng.* 21 (2) (1980) 249–263.
- [41] Z. Bazant, M. Christensen, Analogy between micropolar continuum and grid frameworks under initial stress, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 8 (1972) 327–346.
- [42] A. K. Noor, Continuum modeling for repetitive lattice structures, *Appl. Mech. Rev.* 41 (7) (1988) 285–296.
- [43] R. S. Kumar, D. L. McDowell, Generalized continuum modeling of 2-D periodic cellular solids, *Int. J. Solids*

- Struct. 41 (26) (2004) 7399–7422.
- [44] J. Romanoff, J. Reddy, J. Jelovica, Using non-local timoshenko beam theories for prediction of micro- and macro-structural responses, *Compos. Struct.* 156 (2016) 410–420.
 - [45] J. Romanoff, H. Remes, G. Socha, M. Jutila, P. Varsta, The stiffness of laser stake welded T-joints in web-core sandwich structures, *Thin Wall. Struct.* 45 (4) (2007) 453–462.
 - [46] T. Kant, J. R. Kommineni, C_0 finite element geometrically non-linear analysis of fibre reinforced composite and sandwich laminates based on a higher-order theory, *Comput. Struct.* 45 (3) (1992) 511–520.
 - [47] R. D. Wood, O. C. Zienkiewicz, Geometrically nonlinear finite element analysis of beams, frames, arches and axisymmetric shells, *Comput. Struct.* 7 (6) (1977) 725–735.
 - [48] J. Reddy, *An Introduction to Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis: with applications to heat transfer, fluid mechanics, and solid mechanics*, Oxford University Press, 2015.
 - [49] R. Cook, D. Malkus, M. Plesha, *Concepts and applications of finite element analysis*, John Wiley & Sons, 1989.
 - [50] C. Libove, R. Hubka, Elastic constants for corrugated-core sandwich plates, *Tech. rep.*, NACA (1951).
 - [51] C. Sun, R. Vaidya, Prediction of composite properties from a representative volume element, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 56 (2) (1996) 171–179.
 - [52] M. H. Ghayesh, H. Farokhi, A. Gholipour, Vibration analysis of geometrically imperfect three-layered shear-deformable microbeams, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 122 (2016) 370–383.
 - [53] A. M. Dehrouyeh-Semnani, M. Dehrouyeh, M. Torabi-Kafshgari, M. Nikkhah-Bahrami, A damped sandwich beam model based on symmetric deviatoric couple stress theory, *Int. J. Eng. Sci.* 92 (2015) 83–94.